

Modern Solutions for Correction of Nasal Septum without Tamponade and their Disadvantages

Qiyomov Ikhtiyor Ergashevich

Department of Clinical Pharmacology, Samarkand State Medical University

Abstract: Nasal diseases, which often significantly limit a person's quality of life, require careful diagnosis. To determine the causes of nasal congestion, rhinitis, snoring, sinusitis and headache, our doctors use the most modern examination methods: nasal endoscopy, pressure measurement, rhinomanometry, computer tomography, x-ray examination of the paranasal sinuses.

Key words: Septum, Septoplasty, conservative and operative methods.

After the diagnosis, the optimal treatment method is determined - conservative or, if necessary, surgical treatment.

Profile of a woman's face with closed eyes and makeup Nasal septum surgery, nasal septum correction with reduction of nasal turbinates is the most common ENT operation in adults. It solves problems such as nasal breathing disorders, snoring, frequent infections of the jaw and frontal sinuses. Usually, surgery corrects two anatomical structures of the nose. First, the bone and cartilage structure of the nasal septum is corrected. Then the turbinates (corpus cavernosa) are reduced to allow air to flow into the nose.

Traditional method: operations with tamponade

During traditional operations with scissors, turbinate tissue is reduced. At the end of the operation, tampons are inserted into the vascular mucosa to stop bleeding for 3-4 days. Complications often arise when removing tampons - the nasal septum, which has not yet been fully established, can bend again, as the tampon dries in the newly operated place.

Disadvantages of the traditional method:

It is impossible to breathe through the nose for three to four days after the operation.

Ichor separated from the nose flows through the throat.

Tear fluid cannot escape through the nose, causing bilateral tearing from the eye.

Disruption of sinus ventilation creates pressure on the forehead and cheekbones.

Stationary required.

A new method of correcting the nasal septum is silicone splints

ct-small The new method of nasal septum repair is as follows: under general anesthesia, a small incision is made in the nasal septum, through which defects in the cartilage and bone structure of the nasal septum are corrected. With this method of correction, at the end of the operation, silicone plates are placed to support the corrected septum for splints (repair), which are removed almost painlessly after 2-3 weeks (the patient can remove the plates at home, at the ENT doctor can throw.). The peculiarity of this technique is that tampons are not inserted during these operations. This operation is an outpatient procedure. The patient experiences almost no pain and usually breathes through the nose immediately after the operation.

Advantages of the new technique: Dr. Friedrich

Breathing through the nose is usually possible immediately after the operation.

Only from time to time you can expect minor sleep disturbances.

The operation is performed on an outpatient basis;

The result of the operation is only a slight swelling of the nasal mucosa.

The patient has only small nasal airway disorders.

Silicone plates do not dry on the wound and are easily removed.

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